

Karlstad University CoARA Action Plan

Version 2, Dec 2025

Karlstad University (KAU), www.kau.se, is a mid-sized higher education institution based around two campuses in central Sweden. As a former college, it was granted full university status in 1999. It currently provides around 70 degree programmes and 900 courses in Arts, Humanities, Social Studies, Natural Sciences, Technology, Teaching, and Health Care. At present, it has approximately 20,000 students and 1,300 employees. Overall, KAU's research and education programmes have a broad scope, positioning the university well for engagement in successful collaborations with partners at the regional, national, and international levels. Underlying KAU's long-term vision is a commitment to systematically promote sustainable social, economic, and environmental development. With this in mind, the university provides expertise in the utilisation of research and education in co-operation with a range of partners in wider society, from private industry to public bodies.

Karlstad University signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in May 2023. Since then, the university has actively been raising awareness of the research assessment reform across the university.

We hereby provide an updated KAU CoARA Action Plan that all CoARA signatories are to submit after the first year of signing the agreement. KAU aims to communicate progression annually and provide a conclusive report on adherence to the principles and implementation of the commitments by 2027.

Relevance of Advancing Research Assessment for KAU.

As part of KAU's overarching quality assurance system (C2019/1027), the university is already committed to the topic of responsible research assessment by recognizing the use of qualitative measures in the internal monitoring of research and basing its periodic reviews of research on external peer-review assessments and the responsible use of quantitative indicators.

Karlstad University will adopt and adhere to the National Joint Framework for Merit Assessment, adopted by The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institution's (SUHF) General Assembly on 22 October 2025. SUHF's national framework provides a comprehensive and holistic view of academic contributions within Swedish higher education. Alignment with this framework enables KAU to ensure consistency with national policy developments, reinforce coherence with European reform efforts under CoARA, and support a fair, transparent, and inclusive assessment culture.

In addition, KAU actively engages in HR Excellence in Research, a related initiative with the aim to align HR practices with European standards for researchers.

KAU will continue to appreciate the intricate diversity in research contributions and career development paths to ensure a fair and inclusive assessment environment. To harmonize its practices with the principles of responsible assessment upheld by CoARA, KAU will prioritize and focus on the following areas during the period 2023-2027:

1. **Upholding the Integrity and Quality of Research:** This is achieved by acknowledging rigorous peer-review assessments and responsible use of indicators.
2. **Recognizing Collaborative Practices:** Practices for collaboration with the surrounding society is seen as a key instrument for enhancing quality in both research and education.
3. **Endorsing Open Science Practices:** Open science practices is recognized as a testament to quality in research and education.
4. **Advancing Academic Career Assessments:** The evaluation of academic careers is advanced by recognizing a broader and qualitative spectrum of merits.

Planned activities on the topic of Advancing Research Assessment.

The university has aligned with both national and international stakeholders in the same time as evolving local practices in research assessment. While possible more actions will be implemented over the coming years, the university plans to carry out the following activities up until 2027.

1. Actively participate in the framework of the Swedish National Chapter chaired by SUHF, Sweden.
2. Monitor, and take into account, for local implementation, recommendations presented by CoARA working groups, on a national and international level.
3. Review and, when relevant, adjust KAU research assessment practises in relation to the principles and core commitments of CoARA. This will involve:
 - a) With the support of the overarching quality assurance system, develop an overview of the assessment processes of research or researchers at KAU.
 - b) When appropriate and in the light of the prioritization areas of KAU, develop criteria, tools and procedures in line with the core commitments.

During 2026, a special emphasis will be placed on recognizing collaborative practices in recruitment and promotion through the project The Merit Pathway. The Merit Pathway aims to strengthen the recognition of both utilisation and collaborative competence as academic merits. The reason behind this is that our research and education are characterised by close relationships with the surrounding society, and collaboration remains a key strategy for continuous quality development. Through the Merit Pathway, KAU hopes to advance a culture where collaboration, engagement, and societal contribution are integral parts of academic excellence and career progression.

4. Raise awareness of reforming research assessment. Provide assesses and assessors the opportunity to understand and adopt to the new assessment principles and instructions.
5. In the light of CoARA, communicate international, national and institutional development on the KAU website.

KAU implementation plan for change

KAU actions to implement changes in assessment practices. The CoARA Core Commitments (i.e. what to change) and Supporting Commitments (i.e. how to change) as defined by the Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment.

Core Commitment	Action	Completed
1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.	1.1 Adopt and adhere to the National Joint Framework for Merit Assessment, adopted by The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institution's (SUHF) General Assembly on 22 October 2025.	Ongoing
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.	2.1 Periodic Research Reviews at KAU are primarily based on self-evaluations and peer-reviews supported by relevant and responsible use of quantitative data.	2024
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.	3.1 Provide guidance to applicants, external reviewers and appointment panels to apply appropriate metrics for promotions.	
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.	4.1 As of 2026, KAU will no longer submit data to the Times Higher Education (THE) Rankings. The decision demonstrates the university's commitment to research assessment which is transparent, open and focused on the true impact of its activities.	2025
Supporting Commitment		
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.	5.1 Internal CoARA working group established to monitor progression and identify local development needs.	Ongoing
	5.2 Actively Participate in the Swedish National Chapter's Governance and Agenda - Member of Steering group - Chairing working group 5 - Part of working groups: WG1: National Research Applications WG2: Assessment of Individual Academics WG3: Responsible Bibliometrics WG5: Collaboration and Valorization	Ongoing
	5.3 Continue to provide support for implementing the European Charter for	Ongoing

	<p>Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.</p> <p>5.4 Continue to highlight and discuss development needs in relation to CoARA within KAU Quality Council.</p> <p>5.5 Pro-Vice Chancellor engaged in the working group for Merit Assessment, within SUHF – Joint Framework for merit assessment adopted in autumn of 2025</p> <p>5.6 Vice-Chancellor engaged in the working group for Quality Assurance within SUHF – Revision of Joint Framework for quality assurance of research planned for 2026.</p> <p>5.7 KALEIDOS, a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Research Executive Agency, aims at developing policys and tools for Knowledge Valorization.</p> <p>5.8 Within the EUNICE university alliance, Karlstad University has collaboratively developed a joint Access to Knowledge Policy to promote open and equitable sharing of research and educational resources.</p>	<p>Ongoing</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>2025</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>2025</p>
<p>6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.</p>	<p>6.1 During 2023–2024, the university conducted a comprehensive review of the Quality assurance system for research and its associated governance documents. Supporting data now includes a larger proportion of qualitative information, such as the number of peer-review assignments, affiliated researchers, and collaborative partners.</p> <p>6.2 Submit Proposal for the 2nd call of CoARA Cascade funding</p> <p>6.3 Revision of KAU Publication Policy in adherence with CoARA and the National Guidelines for Open Science, published by the National Library of Sweden (KB 2024-42)</p> <p>6.4 The Merit Pathway – Review assessment criteria and assessment practice of collaborative skills in recruitment and promotion processes</p>	<p>2024</p> <p>2025</p> <p>Start 2026</p> <p>Start 2026</p>

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	7.1 Open information sessions 7.2 Priority settings and key areas for KAU CoARA Action Plan were identified in consultation with the professors' collegium at KAU	2023-24 2024
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.	8.1 As a member of CoARA, KAU agrees to communicate progress made and exchange good practice with relevant networks. 8.2 Pro-Vice Chancellor Chairing KLOSSnet, a network where collaboration leaders at management level of Swedish HEIs work together to strengthen and develop strategic collaboration in research and education. 8.3 Knowledge exchange for promoting international relevance of CoARA with partner universities; University of South Eastern Norway and University of Vaasa, Finland. 8.4 KAU representative in Inorms Research Evaluation Group.	Ongoing Ongoing Ongoing Ongoing
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.	9.1 Publish Version 1. KAU CoARA Action Plan on University website and Zenodo 9.2 Publish Version 2. KAU CoARA Action Plan on University website and Zenodo 9.3 Communicate progression by seminars and on the university website	2024 2025
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on re-search, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research		

Contact:

Legal representative, Pro-Vice-Chancellor, Professor Margareta Friman,

margareta.friman@kau.se

Operational matters, Research Advisor, Sofia Andersson, sofia.andersson@kau.se